

From reuse to impact: monitoring data reuse in CESSDA archives

Filippo Accordino¹⁻² [0000-0002-4245-0654], Daniela Luzi¹⁻² [0000-0003-3404-3271]
and Fabrizio Pecoraro¹⁻² [0000-0001-5718-4240]

¹ Institute for Research on Population and Social Policies, National Research Council,
Rome, Italy

² Data Archive for Social Sciences in Italy, Rome, Italy

Abstract. This contribution presents a lightweight script to monitor and evaluate the reuse of research data in CESSDA archives. It collects citations of data, integrates metadata, and produces basic metrics to assess data impact over time. The tool supports researchers and data stewards in understanding the value of data sharing and promoting informed data management.

Conference Themes: Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment, Transparency and Inclusivity of Assessment Processes, Recognition of Contributions to Open Science

Keywords: data reuse, data citation, data sharing, tracking data, CESSDA.

1 Introduction

The process of tracking data reuse, i.e. the utilisation of extant material to address novel research questions, is a challenging one. The problem may be ascribed to two principal factors: technical reasons, and secondly, inaccurate citation practices among scholars. The Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles (JDDCP) asserts the status of data as a product of research and advocates for their accurate citation in accordance with a standardised protocol (1). This protocol encompasses the citation of authors, archives, titles, and Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs), among other bibliographic details.

A plethora of methodologies have been advanced in the literature to facilitate the tracking of data reuse (2–5). However, the implementation of these methodologies remains challenging for technical reasons and due to the absence of optimal citation practices. The most accurate approach to this issue is to count the citations of data within the bibliographic references of scientific publications.

The contribution presents an automatic method by which archives belonging to the CESSDA-ERIC research infrastructure (6) can track the re-use of deposited data (7). The authors have developed and shared a script in R language (8) that utilises a list of DOIs to track the reuse of data, when cited in the publications indexed on Scopus. The script also facilitates the acquisition of an overview of the cited data, with their characteristics described through the same metadata exposed in the CESSDA catalogue. The contribution also aims to underline the importance of correctly citing

data, not least in order to measure the extent to which it is reused and, therefore, its impact.

2 Relevance to conference themes

The identification of data reuse is crucial in measuring data impact (2) and to produce quality metrics that are pivotal in the evaluation process of the research infrastructures that hold them (9,10). It is also beneficial for data authors to comprehend which research communities are interested in their data and the manner in which it has been reused.

3 Significance and relation to existing work

Data archives frequently utilise metrics based on data downloads, page views, or links (2,11) to assess the reuse of their data. While these methods are practical from a technical point of view (12), the results can be misleading (13) and do not necessarily indicate real reuse. Some literature proposes alternative metrics for the assessment of reusability as opposed to reuse. The present study adopts a different methodological approach, considering citations to datasets as a tangible, evident and unquestionable form of data reuse or strong researcher interest (14,15).

4 Novelty

This study proposes an original procedure and provides a script, shared on DASSI's Github, that will be of use to CESSDA archives. The tool facilitates the tracking of data reuse and the description thereof through the utilisation of metadata. Moreover, the study demonstrates a manner in which certain technical and practical limitations in measuring data reuse can be surmounted. In the future, it may be possible to adapt the script to extract data from other indexing services that allow searches to be performed using references of the scientific papers.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest relevant to this manuscript.

References

1. Data Citation Synthesis Group: Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles. Force11 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.25490/A97F-EGYK>.
2. Ball, A., Duke, M.: How to Track the Impact of Research Data with Metrics. Edinburgh: Digital Curation Centre. (2015). <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/how-guides>.
3. He, L., Nahar, V.: Reuse of scientific data in academic publications. *Aslib Journal of Information Management*. **68**(4), 478–494 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1108/ajim-01-2016-0008>.

4. Khan, N., Pink, C.J., Thelwall, M.: Identifying Data Sharing and Reuse with Scholix: Potentials and Limitations. *Patterns*. **1**(1), 100007 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2020.100007>.
5. Mannheimer, S., Sterman, L., Borda, S.: Discovery and Reuse of Open Datasets: An Exploratory Study. *JeSLIB*. **5**(1), e1091 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.7191/jeslib.2016.1091>.
6. Accordino, F., Pecoraro, F., Luzi, D.: CESSDA data catalogue: an opportunity to enhance data in social sciences. *Int J Digit Libr* **26**(1), 8 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00799-025-00416-w>
7. Accordino, F., Luzi, D., Pecoraro, F.: Challenges in tracking archive's data reuse in social sciences. *Digit Libr Perspect* **41**(2), 189–206 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1108/DLP-07-2024-0112>
8. The R Core Team, R: A language and environment for statistical computing, <https://cran.r-project.org/doc/manuals/r-release/fullrefman.pdf>, last accessed 2025/09/27
9. ESFRI, ESFRI WG REPORT - Monitoring of Research Infrastructures Performance, <https://www.esfri.eu/monitoring-research-infrastructures-performance-december-2019>, last accessed 2025/09/27
10. Umbrich, J., Neumaier, S., Polleres, A.: Quality Assessment and Evolution of Open Data Portals, 3rd International Conference on Future Internet of Things and Cloud, Rome, Italy, pp. 404-411 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ficloud.2015.82>.
11. Bishop, L., Kuula-Luumi, A.: Revisiting Qualitative Data Reuse: A Decade On. *SAGE Open* **7**(1), (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244016685136>.
12. Mayernik, M.S., Hart, D.L., Maull, K.E., Weber, N.M.: Assessing and tracing the outcomes and impact of research infrastructures. *J Assoc Inf Sci Technol* **68**(6), 1341–1359 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.23721>.
13. Pasquetto, I. V., Borgman, C. L., & Wofford, M. F.: Uses and Reuses of Scientific Data: The Data Creators' Advantage. *Harvard Data Science Review*, 1(2), (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1162/99608f92.fc14bf2d>.
14. Endris, K.M., Giménez-García, J.M., Thakkar, H., Demidova, E., Zimmermann, A., Lange, C., Simperl, E.: Dataset Reuse: An Analysis of References in Community Discussions, Publications and Data. In: *Proceedings of the Knowledge Capture Conference (K-CAP)*, p. 1–4 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3148011.3154461>.
15. Kenfield, A.S., Woolcott, L., Thompson, S., Kelly, E.J., Shiri, A., Muglia, C., Masood, K., Chapman, J., Jefferson, D., Morales, M.E.: Toward a definition of digital object reuse. *Digit Libr Perspect* **38**(3), 378–394 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1108/dlp-06-2021-0044>.